

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20052971

CHANGE MANAGEMENT AND CORPORATE SOCIAL PERFORMANCE: A NEXUS FOR ORGANISATIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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Received: 02/04/2026
Accepted: 23/04/2026

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ABSTRACT

The study examines the interconnection that exist between change management and corporate social performance in sustaining organisational development. This study used a sample frame of 458 employees from four selected Fmcgs firms within the southwestern geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) with partial least squares was used to test the hypotheses. The findings for the overall sample revealed a direct, positive and significant impact of unambiguous communication, change adaptability and reform sensitization on corporate social performance, while influencer support and new competencies for self-management were found insignificant. This makes it logical for emphasizes on a well-communicated reform for participatory roles, while adopting adaptability for social-driven organisations.

KEYWORDS: Change adaptability, Influencer support, Competencies for self-management, Reform sensitization, Unambiguous communication, Fmcgs.

1. INTRODUCTION

The dynamism of the present business environment has made it necessary for corporate organisations to build capacity, by engaging in a planned change towards organisational development. This business environment is characterised by constant flux and gaps identified within the work processes that spurs the need for re-integrating the internal strategies in conforming to the external changes (Cummings & Worley, 2019; Doroshuk, 2019). To this end, this makes organisational development to be multifaceted and considered as indispensable in the performance processes of organisation as it generates innovative ideas that permeate competencies (Dotse, Okyireh & Kumako, 2015; Pinnington, Aldabbas, Mirshahi, & Pirie, 2022). Odor (2018); Stouten, Rousseau and De Cremer (2018) attests to this practice of organisational development in corporate organizations operating in different sectors in improving their functionality, as well as influencing proficient direction for their operations. Whereas incorporating organisational development comes at the instance of need for change in processes, policies, or the cultural practices of the work environment (Knight & Parker, 2021; Cummings & Worley, 2019; Odor, 2018; Marshak & Bushe, 2018). Extant studies have shown these practices either as a total reformation, an improvement on existing structure, through a total quality management for the customers focus, or the redevelopment of the human capital (Hanelt, Bohnsack, Marz, & Marante 2021; Solanky, Okeke & Aduba, 2019). Therefore, accomplishing this practice is functional to identifying, and quick response to changes in the business environment (Ahmadi, Baei & Sharifii, 2017; Anderson, 2018; Okoro, 2018).

Focusing on previous research, change management essentially fosters the crystallisation of new possibilities within the work processes which improves social performance, as these are expressed in activities of positive impact on the society (Rosenbaum, More, & Steane, 2018). In other words, it is consequential that this well-implemented change management through the interaction of social performance are displayed as a proactive behaviour in making ethical initiative moves (Da Ros, Vainieri, & Bellé, 2023). But studies have shown that, social performance appears to be of more value and well established in the developed economy, while developing countries are yet to fully embrace it (Yumei, Iqbal, Nurunnabi, Abbas, Jingde, & Chaudhry, 2021). Existing literature also revealed that Nigeria as an emerging economy, has about only

87% of its companies listed on the global social responsibility performance database which results to incomplete ratings (Upaa, Ugwoke & Ugwoke, 2018). Meanwhile several other studies pointed out flaws of organisations not ethically, and socially responsible, of which their claim includes; managerial prejudice, shareholders' primacy, also as an addition cost to organisations (Aguinis & Glavas, 2012; Berger-Walliser, 2018).

Consequently, Fmcgs industries in Nigeria have not received sufficient attention as most studies on social performance has its focuses from the oil and gas, telecommunications, multinationals, also the banking sector (Ifeoma, Purity, & Patient, 2021; Napier, Knight, Luo & Delios, 2023). Therefore, debating on the sustainable concerns of performance of change management on social performance in Fmcgs, this study considers some factors of change management as it provides response to the hypotheses tested such as; reform sensitization, change adaptability, influencer support, new competencies for self- management, unambiguous communication can positively influence social performance (Stouten, et al, 2018; Al-Haddad & Kotnour, 2015; Subramaniam & Jaganathan, 2021; Bel, Smirnov & Wait, 2018).

In so much as change management involves finding a new or improved ways of using resources to create value which entails reordering the existing processes, it is determined by exigencies that arises in the process. It is in this uniqueness is that organisation differs in contingencies as well as in its operations and structures (Licandro, Burguete, Ortigueira-Sánchez, & Correa, 2024). Therefore, it is imperative for this study to know how the management of change while putting into consideration factors of influence, and the process of social performance among the FMCGs can be of benefit towards organisational development.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Accordingly, contingency model of change management argues for change strategies by managers or consultants in optimizing performances, while considering some exigencies that may arise in the course of the event (Dunphy & Stace, 1993). This model advances the work of Lewin's change model, that popularizes a three-step perception for a need for change, then the actualizing this change and lastly, experiencing the new norm of change. However, the contingency model takes cognizance of differences in cultural values, work processes, structures or environmental factors that are peculiar to organisations, thereby the manager

taking a different approach to the change process (Samal & Chatterjee, 2020). So, due to these exigences the flow change process may not be as expected. The theory suggests some major incentives for managers in a range of approaches to change while also being mindful of the dynamic environment (Dunphy & Stace, 1993). While embarking on the change programme, the approach works so well specially to achieve performance when engaged in organisational development (Hussain, et al, 2018; Stouten, et al, 2018).

2.1. Change Management

The business environment is ever-evolving, and there is a need for organisations to incorporate and adapt to this changing environment, in order to secure a place in the market (Al-Haddad & Kotnour, 2015; Goel, Kumari, Vaghela, Nagabhyru, Karichalil, Salman, & Brahmane, 2025). In this, organisations integrate the employees' participatory in programmes for the transitioning process for performance implementation, also the choice of introducing and adapting to modern technology or work methods in responds to continuous changing demands, are effective processes of managing change (Daniel, 2019). So, the procedure requires the organisation to clamour for a departure from its present state, to a more all-encompassing desirable level which is usually of more innovative. These changes are inevitable in organisation's processes, and triggered by continuous technological advancement, and increasingly global competitiveness of the business environment (Li, Sun, Tao, & Lee, 2021; Schmidt, Groeneveld & Van de Walle, 2017). There is the emphasis on the future of organisations laying in the hands of the manager that is sensitive to the need for change; and responds to it agilely, to persistently master the change process (Al Bazie & Braganza, 2020; Appelbaum, Cameron, Ensink, Hazarika, Attir, Ezzedine, & Shekhar, 2017). Hussain, Lei, Akram, Haider, Hussain and Ali (2017) define change management as a strategic process which compels the organisation to continually renew its policies, procedures, processes, strategies, structure, and capabilities so as to serve the demand of ever-changing needs of both its internal and external stakeholders. Njuguna and Muathe (2016) study was of the view that change management could be managing a transitional period for individuals, teams, and organisations, from a current to a desired state in making performance a possibility, and this as seen in the programme as a fundamental responsibility. Al-Haddad and Kotnour (2015) opine in their study that change is imminent

for organisations in sustaining their successes and sustainability. Nevertheless, these changes could be projected, or suddenly forced on an organisation as a result of a shift in the business environment, and results to either an incremental or a radical process. However, during this period of reform, the organisation experiences mostly negative reactions as resistance due to the transition, but except for the enthusiasts who are optimistic and shows total support for the reform.

2.1.2. Corporate Social Performance

Organisations are integral part of the environment and largely depend on its growth and sustenance and as such, continuously strives to pattern its activities in line to the nature of output being utilize, the type of production, and how these outputs are distributed in alignment with the social system (Amodu, 2017; Carroll & Shabana, 2010; Jiang, Xue, Lo & Wu, 2019; Oyewumi & Oyewumi, 2017). Social performance is a community responsibility that organisation brings onboard in driving its vision, mission and core values towards making a positive impact in the condition and wellbeing of the host community (Alfalih, 2022; Licandro, et al., 2024; Singha, Rautrao, Chopra, Arora, & Choudhury, 2025). It is also a company's social responsiveness towards its stakeholders, and the environment where the business operates. Furthermore, it is the measurement of organisation's performance in creating social values, either through their products or services; and in achieving the missions, goals, and objectives (Bhattarai, Kwong & Tasavori, 2019; Ujan, 2019). Cudjoe, Abdul Latiff, Abu Kasim, and Bin Osman (2019) also noted in a related development that, company's social responsiveness should be encompassing to ensure both social wellness of the people, as well as safer operating environment. As these companies well-manages their social responsibilities, they achieve an improved social performance, while creating more value for their stakeholders. Bhattarai et al. (2019) though argues that the intended beneficiaries at some times are unable to meet some certain expectations, but organisations should see its social performances as a positive impact to the society. It is of importance to note that as these efforts are progressed to the community, the intention is geared towards targeting and addressing both national and global issues.

2.2. Empirical Review of Literature

Ronnenberg, Graham and Mahmoodi (2011) examined change management efforts in improving the perceived success of environmental management system (EMS) implementation. The findings were

that efforts of change management enhance the perceived environmental performance, which are primarily driven by the top management. Pana (2013) also in a similar development, studied about the growing social effectiveness of firms through innovativeness in their change management. The findings were hinged on the variables used to ascertain the level of growth of social effectiveness. Ingham and Havard (2017) sought to find out how corporate social responsibility (CSR)-related programs could indicate strategic and organizational changes. The analysis showed the role of central dimensions that supports the integration of CSR programs within the organization. The research was based on case study from a French public utility organisation. Crişan-Mitra, Stanca and Dabija (2020) study further showed interest in the priorities

governing large companies in an emerging market as it regards corporate social performances. The study examined eighty-seven (87) managers of Romanian companies, and the findings came-up with typologies that places emphasis on organisations using corporate social responsibility in gaining their client's trust. Vătămănescu, Dabija, Gazzola, Cegarro-Navarro and Buzzi (2021) also made a submission on consumers' perspective by comparing the frameworks of before and after the outbreak of the covid pandemic, by using nine hundred and seventy-seven (977) respondents. The findings show individual's propensity towards buying sustainable products as contingent to both the social and environmental sustainability practices, and this is also differently applied to every organisation. The review summaries are stated in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary Review of Literature of Change Management and Social Performance.

Authors/ Topics	Region/ Sector	Method Applied	Key Issues Highlighted	Contributions	Gaps
Ronnenberg, et al. (2011). The Important Role of Change Management in Environmental Management System Implementation.	Mid-level engineers and managers in manufacturing facilities.	Survey data analysis.	Examine if change management efforts can improve the perceived success of EMS implementation.	Enhancing the value of firms' EMS implementations.	There is gap of limited data of study.
Pana (2013). Social Efficacy by Responsible Change Management.	Not specified.	Descriptive method.	Change/Innovation management as the main way to grow social effectiveness.	Original contributions of theory-building in social activities, structures, techniques and decision models.	There is gap in empiric studies.
Ingham & Havard (2017). CSR as Strategic and Organizational Change at "Groupe LaPoste"	A French public utilities organization	A case study using semi-structured interview	How the CSR program aims at explaining how the central dimensions are integrated and how they are perceived by key actors.	A progressive convergence between strategic and CSR trajectories and how organization can integrate CSR as a central part of its strategic plan.	The case study is based on a limited number of interviews.
Crişan-Mitra, Stanca & Dabija, (2020). Corporate Social Performance: An Assessment Model on an Emerging Market.	18 Managers from Romania as an emerging market in Eastern Europe.	Exploratory research.	To identify patterns in managerial behavior leading to higher CSP.	Using the CSR behavioral assessment model to facilitate change towards greater CSP.	Limited in sector.
Vătămănescu, Dabija, Gazzola, Cegarro-Navarro & Buzzi (2021). Before and After the Outbreak of Covid-19: Linking Fashion Companies' Corporate Social Responsibility Approach to Consumers'	A total of 977 responses from 693 Generation Z and 284 Millennials generation students.	An empirical investigation using quantitative survey studies	How companies strategically acted and communicated before & after (COVID-19) in relating to choose of sustainable products.	Both CSR approach and corporate reputation have a direct influence on consumers' propensity towards buying sustainable product.	Empirical scrutiny relied on self-reported measure.

Demand for Sustainable Products.					
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2.3 Development of Hypotheses

2.3.1. Reform Sensitization and Corporate Social Performance

As reforms are processed there is the need for higher level of awareness in sensitizing the target group about the intended change, which is a fundamental mechanism to the success of the program. This sensitization is geared towards achieving positive attitude toward the reform process, as well as creating psychological readiness for the members about the reform, while it helps the organisation to address the issue that may arise from resisting the change (Stouten, et al, 2018). Hubbart (2023); Voet and Vermeeren (2016) study viewed it as being crucial to first generate a positive perception of the change among the employee during the reform process, in order to garner maximum support, and reduce to the barest minimum any resistance for the new paradigm. So, to a large extent, the reform process requires the adaptation of the existing strategies and structures into the new form. Adna and Sukoco (2020); study upheld that, the leadership creates an enabling environment for the reform, so that members can readily accept the need for change, while they commit both their physical and psychological energy into it. Hence, individual perception in readiness for the reform can be responsible to positive reactions to organisational changes. As a result, the hypothesis is developed.

Hypothesis 1 (H1). Reform sensitization positively influences social performance.

2.3.2. Change Adaptability and Corporate Social Performance

The management team are often faced with the challenges of resistance from the members as this is due to uncertainties usually perceived by them, as an outcome of the new horizon within which they are expected to operate; hence, adaptability could be seen as a Hercules's task. However, as managers effect these from time-to-time changes, the success is dependable on the level of adaptability, which is subject to identifying the adaptiveness to the available resources, and the degree of knowledge

and skills in making the changes more effective (Al-Haddad & Kotnour, 2015; Muluneh & Gedifew 2018). An adaptive change involves responding to problems by creating a conducive operating system, outside the normal operating system in unleashing a shared responsibilities to those involved, or by building on a capacity a future development (Hanelt, et al, 2021; Muluneh & Gedifew, 2018). Schulze and Pinkow (2020) furthered noted that the ability of an organisation to recognize this need for change, is a function of the level of its preparedness for the new normal. Thus, for a desired successful adaptability is to identify and sense for new opportunities, as such knowledge that will enable managers to effortlessly stir through the seemingly uncertain times into the anticipated destination. Petrou, Demerouti and Schaufeli (2018) however, recognizes the role of willing employees in facilitating and transiting easily during the adaptive process of the organisational change. Therefore, for its values, and in order to enable organisations to maintain a competitive edge, this leads to the following hypothesis.

Hypothesis 2 (H2). Change adaptability positively influences social performance.

2.3.3. Influencer Support and Corporate Social Performance

It is not uncommon scenario during organisational change process to see and feel the uneasiness of the people with the change process. This is due to the perceived uncertainties in view of the new normal they are expected operate in. Oreg, Bartunek, Lee and Do, (2018) study of was of the opinion that the management team is required to develop capacity for the members, in transcending on this path for the effective change process. This involve individuals or groups that can ultimately initiate and be the driver of the move in promoting the desired change (Faupe, & Süß, 2019; Ogbari, 2024). The influencer is a key-driver of the agent for change as he holds both the trust of the management team and their other colleagues. Moreover, it is necessary for the management team to first identify, from among the team anyone who possess the virtue of an agent of change, and earns the confidence of the

group, in order to gain their support during the implementation of the changes (Men, Yue, & Liu, 2020). In addition, an influencer can be an effective instrument that the organisation can leverage upon to inspire, and convince other team mates for their maximum support through his charisma or power influence in orientating the activities (Berne-Manero & Marzo-Navarro, 2020; Wang, Zhang, Chen, Zeng & Cao, 2022). Therefore, this argument advances this hypothesis:

Hypothesis 3 (H3). Influencer support positively influences social performance.

2.3.4. New Competencies for Self-Management and Corporate Social Performance

Change management is complete when the groups or individuals are properly settled in and are acclimatized into their new system. During this process, new competencies are developed for the management of the new status, due to the transition taken placed. As such a lot is expected at this stage which is usually at a higher cost to the organisation as it requires proper orientating in training and developing the members (Subramaniam & Jaganathan, 2021). Neiva, Odelius and Ramos (2015) opines that, the team members undergo a period of learning, unlearning and relearning processes that generates innovative ideas for individuals, and expected conducts of behaviour. The result of this creates a sustainable plan in managing other future activities, and a well-planned managerial structure for effectiveness in the operations (Jackson, 2019; Millikin, Hom & Manz, 2010). In addition, these competencies are built-upon by regular provision of resources for implementing the changes for the workforce, and a supportive system for the agents of the change. Therefore, the reinforcing, incorporating and management of these new activities are needed to establish the desired changes, hence; the hypothesis is established:

Hypothesis 4 (H4). New competencies for self-management positively influences social performance.

2.3.5 Unambiguous Communication and Corporate Social Performance

In response to the impact of constant change in the business environment, organisations find it necessary to engage in reforms, in view of total sustenance of performances. For the success of this change, the manager refocuses on improving the existing processes, while creating the need for a new approach to things (Bel, et al, 2018). This is conceptualized in the level of manager's knowledge

about the change management implementation, its procedures and in the well-communicating to the targeted audience (Christensen, 2014; Hogg, 2018). A growing consensus recognizes that communication has a growing impact in the process of managing change, as it plays crucial roles of either generating and interpreting messages, or doing both in a same directional or bidirectional way (Li, et al, 2021). Malek and Yazdanifard (2012) study observed that in the event of interacting, messages are received and reacted to among the participants because of its explicitness. However, in effective communication is not just the sending and receiving information, but of more necessity for this information to be well understood for necessary actions to be taken. This can be done by simplifying the message for change in clearer terms that is void of any assumption or ambiguities. Adebayo, Worlu, Moses and Ogunnaiké (2020) furthered, attests to higher-level of performance when communicating roles are not ambiguous, but are with precisions. Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 5 (H5). Unambiguous communication positively influences social performance.

3. METHODOLOGY

The population of this study consists of employees from four (4) firms in the FMCGs industry. Data were physically collected through several personal visits of the researchers to the organisations which are all located in the Southwestern part of Nigeria. The respondents were randomly drawn to give the population an equal chance of being selected; while the researcher purposefully select participants based on specific criteria of firms' relevance to the posed research questions. In all, the sampling was convenient based on the availability of the employees during the period of data collection (Etikan, & Babatope, 2019). A total of five hundred and twenty (520) copies of questionnaires were shared to the respondents of which four hundred and fifty-eight (458) were returned, as sixty-two (62) copies of the questionnaires were found either incomplete, or were not properly filled, and such were deemed not valid for the analysis. Therefore, 88.1% response rate were of valid for the analysis, and this stands reasonable enough adjudged to represent the population of the study. In the same vein, Table 2 presents the demographic representation of the sample population.

Table 2. Demographic Representation of the Sample Population

Measure	Value	Frequency	Percentage
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Gender	Male	323	70.3
	Female	135	29.5
Academic Qualification	High School	40	8.7
	Diploma	89	19.5
	Bachelor	217	47.4
	Postgraduate	87	19.0
	Vocational	25	5.5
Age	18- 30years	136	29.7
	31- 40 years	210	45.9
	41- 50 years	76	16.6
	51 years above	36	7.9
Marital Status	Single	168	36.6
	Married	247	53.9
	Others	43	9.4
Work Experience	0-5years	128	27.9
	6-10years	188	41.1
	11-15years	103	22.4
	16years & above	39	8.5

3.1 Questionnaire Design

The questionnaire is made-up of thirty-two (32) items that represents both the independent (change management), and dependent (social performance) variables. The researchers ensured that every selected item was duly tested, with related research instruments from extant literature. The questionnaire is divided into two sections, as the section (A) has five items that addresses the respondents' demographic data. In the bio-data profile of all the employees reported for this study, three hundred and twenty-three (323) males represent 70.3% of the respondents, who are in their active age of 31–40 years to form a 45.9% of the sample population. While, almost half of the total population of the employees which represents 47.4% has a minimum of a first degree as their educational background. However, two hundred and thirty-nine (239) employees who are about 52.19% of the respondents were reportedly married, and a 41.1% of the entire sample population were indicated to have had a minimum of 6-10years work experience.

The section (B) featured 12 items under the change management such as "I am well informed and prepared about any reform before it takes place in my organisation"; "I am developed with new competencies to manage myself in the new transition."; "My organisation needs to gain the support of influencer people before changes can be implemented". Additionally, the social performance was also measured with 12 items such as, "My organisation complies with standards related to safety, and hygiene programmes"; "We operate in a manner that is consistent with the expectations of government and the law"; "In my firm, business integrity goes beyond compliance with laws and

regulations.". The measurement was on a Likert five scale that runs in the range of strongly agree = 5, agree = 4, undecided = 3, disagree = 2, strongly disagree = 1. This enables a participatory that ensured answers given were within the scale.

However, in order to guide against bias responses, participants were allowed to give a more comprehensive view of the subject matter through the open-ended questions as related to each research item. Aguirre-Urreta and Hu (2019) study attests to bias responses given by the respondents, which may cause a potential common method variance and ultimately, result could lead to a false internal consistency of validity of the results presented from the data. The open-ended questions were also designed to facilitate respondents' rich levels of knowledge, in their proficiency of the subject matter, and to further enrich the discussions.

4. MEASUREMENT AND ANALYSIS

The stated hypotheses were tested and analyzed with the smart PLS and Structural Equation Modelling (PLS_SEM). The is to find the structural path co-efficient (R2) of each construct through PLS Algorithm Model, PLS Bootstrapping Model with β and P values, and the PLS Bootstrapping Model with β and T values to measure, and to determine the level of significance influence of change management on social performance. The algorithm was used to calculate and determine the path co-efficient and the significant values, while the bootstrapping determined the significant testing of the coefficient. Moreover, the bootstrapping model was programmed by default at 500 sub-samples which affirms the use of it in achieving significant results (Ringle, Sarstedt, Mitchell & Gudergan, 2020). The test of the hypotheses also helps to determine the adequacy of the statistical proof as it shows evidence either in support or against the formulated hypotheses.

Figure 1 shows the PLS algorithm model of change management and social performance. The pathways showed in details the resultant effect and the internal consistency in the level of relationship among the variables with the R square (R2) values showing the level of variance as this is calculated to be 0.815 for change management. This implies that all the factor loading items of social performance significantly explains 81.5% of the variance in change management. Therefore, change management shows positive relationship with social performance. In a similar relation, Figure 2 also depicts that change management collectively explained 0.903 of the variability of social performance. This implies that all

the items that measured change management reasonably explain 90.3% of the variance in social performance. Figure 3 presents the standard β coefficient and smart PLS path coefficients which are both similar. The β value indicates the expected variance in the social performance for a unit variation in change management. This was used to test the significance of hypotheses formulated as any increase in β value, gives a resultant effect on change management.

Figure 1. PLS algorithm model.

Figure 2. PLS bootstrapping model with β and P values.

Figure 3. PLS bootstrapping model with β and T values.

Table 3: Path co-efficient.

Variables	Loadings	T Statistics	P Values	Path Co-efficient	R ²
Structural Path					
Change Management → Social Performance		51.064	0.000	0.903	0.815
Importance-Performance Map					
Measurement				performances	Importance
Reform Sensitisation	0.725	14.438	0.000	62.667	0.272
Change Adaptability	0.707	12.616	0.000	62.500	0.297
Influencer Support	0.618	7.476	0.000	62.500	0.213
New Competencies for Self-Mgt	0.672	10.024	0.000	63.167	0.210
Unambiguous Communication	0.743	11.557	0.000	58.083	0.300
SPq1	0.826	21.329	0.000		
SPq2	0.774	14.143	0.000		
SPq3	0.649	11.277	0.000		
SPq4	0.707	13.338	0.000		
SPq5	0.891	29.402	0.000		
SPq6	0.870	31.256	0.000		
Cronbach Alpha	Change Management			0.733	
	Social Performance			0.876	
Composite Reliability	Change Management			0.823	
	Social Performance			0.908	
	Change Management			0.582	

AVE	Social Performance	0.625
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The significant effect of change management on social performance was verified through the T-statistical test as Table 3 presents the path co-efficient.

4.1. Discussion of Findings

Figure 1, 2, 3 and Table 3 depict the PLS statistical results for the structural model of hypotheses tested. This study also discovers that the structural path co-efficient of the measures for change management i.e., reform sensitization, change adaptability, influencer support, new competencies for self-management, and unambiguous communication indicates a significant relationship at 0.05. In addition, the result revealed that reform sensitization significantly influences social performance at (T-value=14.438 >1.96, P-value =0.000<0.05). Similarly, it also revealed that change adaptability had significant influence on social performance at (T-value= 12.616 >1.96, P-value =0.000 <0.05), while influencers support also had significant influence on social performance at (T-value= 7.476 >1.96, P-value =0.000 <0.05). Also in a related development, the result showed that new competencies for self-management had significant influence on social performance at (T-value=10.024 >1.96, P-value =0.000 <0.05), while unambiguous communication also had significant influences social performance at (T-value= 11.557 >1.96, P-value =0.000 <0.05).

In a nutshell, the path co-efficient showed that the level of influence of change management on social performance is statistically significant at ($\beta=0.903$, $R^2=0.815$, T-value =51.064, P-value=0.000<0.05). This implies that change management has significant influence on social performance. Generally, the R^2 of 0.815 suggests 81.5% influence on principal variable i.e. if one unit of change management increases, then 81.5% social performance will increase. In terms of importance, unambiguous communication is the most important variable among the five measured for change management with 0.300, followed by change adaptability with 0.297, then reform sensitization with 0.272, influencer support with 0.213, and finally new competencies for self-management with 0.210 had the least importance with a score of 0.05. Ronnenberg, et al, (2011) examined change management efforts in improving the perceived success of environmental management system implementation and as such aligns with the findings. As a result, change management is driven by top management to enhance their performance as it was suggested from the findings of (Ingham & Havard, 2017). Pana's (2013) study also corroborates as change management associated with innovative social thinking was seen as a significant driver to

grow social effectiveness. It is also logical for the FMCGs firms to invest more on the variables with high performance-importance, while adequate attention is given to variables having least influence on the target construct of social performance (Crişan-Mitra et al, 2020).

4.2. Conclusion, Managerial Implications and Recommendations

This study's main significance is its contribution to the underdeveloped area of nexus of change management, corporate social performance and organisational performance in the Fmcgs industry. While it is recognized that change management strategies impact the level of social performance in an organisation which can either support or hinder the implementation of organisational development, little is known about this association in the context of the Fmcgs industry. It is found that change management and social performance have a positive and statistically significant association in the sampled Fmcgs industries. The relationship was investigated in the light of contingency model of change management in firms. It is, probably, the first study that adopted this theory in the focus of change management and social performance.

In general, the outcomes of this study expand the understanding of the ways and conditions to improve social performance by considering the various concepts of change management. Also, this research reveals an original perspective of measures for the context of change management which has not be used in extant literature or likewise in any association with social performance leading to organisational development. The study also highlights the significant role of practicing unambiguous communication, and thus suggests to the managers and policy makers to provide a supportive environment that also facilitate change adaptability activities and contribute to enhancing reform sensitization of the employees during the change program.

4.3. Limitations and future directions

The study has also some limitations which are to be addressed in the future. The target population for the study is limited only to Southwestern part of Nigeria, where most of the Fmcgs industries have their headquarters located. The results obtained from the region may differ from other locations of the rest geo-political zones of Nigeria, considering different

areas operating in diverse cultural, environmental and political conditions. So future study can be extended to other geo-political zones to increase reliability and allow generalization of the findings. Another limitation pertaining to the definition of change management could be overcome in future by including a different dimension of change management. Likewise, the use of only the quantitative approach to measure the opinions of the respondents may be unidimensional with only 5 choices on the Likert scale, where the space between the choices might not be equidistant; therefore, it may fail to measure the true opinion of the respondents. Moreover, in the future event of considering a

qualitative approach as an additional tool of measure to cater for the likely lapses that may have occurred in the quantitative approach, it is unlikely that respondents' responses would be influenced by heavily concentrate on one response side of (agree/disagree). Finally, this study focused mainly on employee and managerial perspectives, but for future study another approach for consideration is that, studies could look at the perspectives of other stakeholders such as the clients/customers to also analyse their behaviour and attitudes concerning social performance and change management contexts.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS: The authors would especially like to express their gratitude to the administration of Covenant University Centre for Research, Innovation and Discovery (CUCRID) which is the hub for research financial support and technical processes.

Author Contributions: All authors whose names appear in this manuscript of paper contributed to the study conception and design. material preparation, data collection and analysis were performed by OPA, while Title suggestions; first draft of the manuscript were carried out by JOK and MEO. In addition, DEU and SIK did the final editing and proofreading of the manuscript. Conversely, all authors contributed in one way or the other to the success of the first and the final versions of the manuscript.

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